

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART VIII. A DISCUSSION ON THE VISCOSITY OF RESINS, CELLULOSE DERIVATIVES, ETC IN MIXED SOLVENTS.

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Viscosity data obtained for lyophilic solutes, e.g., resins, cellulose derivatives, etc. in mixed solvents have been examined from theoretical and experimental considerations. It has been shown that the results are qualitatively in agreement with the classical equations on viscosity. The conditions for the occurrence and position of the minimum viscosity have been discussed and the results have been generalised in the shape of a rule, deductions from which have been shown to be in accord with the available data.

The present communication is an analysis of the results presented in some previous papers (Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 663; 1942, 19, 207) of this series, to correlate them with the available data on a common background. Mention may, however, be made of the work of various authors who attempted to correlate the solvent power and viscosity of solutions of resins and nitrocellulose with the oxygen content of the solvent, the presence of polar groups, molecular volume, etc. with only limited success. The author's main observations and results have been summarised in the previous paper and discussion will be made without any further reference to them.

Mathematical Analysis.

It is of interest to examine how far our result can be fitted into the existing equations of viscosity. Let us assume that the viscosity curve of the pure solvent mixture be of a simple type, without exhibiting maximum or minimum, as given by the equation of Kendall and Munroe (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1802).

$$\eta_0^{\frac{1}{2}} = x\eta_1^{\frac{1}{2}} + (1-x)\eta_2^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where x is the mol-fraction of the component whose viscosity is η_1 , η_2 is the viscosity of the other component, and η_0 that of the mixture. If now progressively increasing amounts of a lyophilic solute are added to the solvent mixtures, each point on the curve would rise up vertically corresponding to

* For discussion, *vide* Bancroft "Applied Colloid Chemistry" 1942, p. 381; Doolittle, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1938, 30, 189.

a rapid increase of viscosity with increase of concentration. Various equations have been proposed to represent viscosity variation with concentration, of which we shall examine the most classical one—the exponential equation of Arrhenius, which can be put as

$$\log \eta = \log \eta_0 + kc \quad \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

where η is the viscosity of the solution and η_0 , that of the solvent mixture, c represents concentration of the solute and k is a constant. Combining these two equations, we get a generalised equation representing at any composition of the solvent mixture any concentration of the solute. The combined equation is

$$\log \eta = 3 \log \{px + q(1-x)\} + kc \quad \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

where p and q stand for $\eta_1^{\frac{1}{3}}$, and $\eta_2^{\frac{1}{3}}$ respectively. The constant k has certainly not the same value for all compositions of the solvent mixture, but is an unknown function of x . So we may put $\phi(x)$ for k when we get

$$\log \eta = 3 \log \{px + q(1-x)\} + \phi(x).c$$

This equation can show a minimum with respect to x -axis, when the first partial differential of viscosity vanishes, i.e., $\partial\eta/\partial x = 0$. Now differentiating with respect to x , we get (iii, a) which for minima in the viscosity curves, gives equation (iv).

$$\frac{1}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial\eta}{\partial x} = \frac{3(p-q)}{px + q(1-x)} + c \cdot \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \quad \dots \text{ (iii, a)}$$

$$\text{or} \quad c \cdot \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} = \frac{3(q-p)}{px + q(1-x)} \quad \dots \text{ (iv)}$$

This equation gives the concentration, c of the solute which will produce minimum viscosity at any given composition, x of the solvent mixture. This equation cannot be utilised, unless ϕ is explicitly known as a function of x , which can only be done by empirical means. But it can elucidate one important point, that the viscosity minimum approaches the optimum composition with increase in concentration of the solute. In other words, we have to find out the condition under which c becomes very high. Evidently, from equation (iv) when

$$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \rightarrow 0, \quad c \rightarrow \infty.$$

But $\partial\phi/\partial x = 0$ is the condition for a minimum in $\phi(x)$. Then it follows that to whatever extent the concentration may increase, the viscosity minimum

would tend to approach the composition for which the Arrhenius constant $k = \phi(x)$ is a minimum. A minimum in k implies the optimum solvent composition by definition. Hence, we have thus theoretically derived, within the very restricted validity of the starting equations (i) and, (ii) our main experimental observation that the viscosity minimum does not occur at a fixed solvent composition, but tends to approach the optimum solvent composition with increase of solute concentration. Hence, not viscosity, as is often loosely stated, but *some function of viscosity*, which is unaffected by the concentration of the solute, should be found out for comparison of solvent power. Baker (*cf.* Doolittle, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1938, 30, 195, 199)

adopted the constant $ak = \left(\frac{\partial \log \eta}{\partial c} \right)_{c \rightarrow 0}$ in his parabolic equation, $\eta = \eta_0(1 + ac)^4$ and McBain utilised the average Arrhenius constant,

$$k = \frac{1}{c} \log \eta / \eta_c$$

for dilute solutions, to compare the solvent power for nitrocellulose (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 312).

Discussion of the Position of the Viscosity Minimum.

The viscosity curves of the pure solvent mixtures we have used, have mostly no maximum or minimum point, but conform to the usual type of having a slight sag, *i.e.*, convex towards the x -axis, as shown in Fig. 1 (lowest curve). Let us now consider what happens when progressively increasing amounts of a lyophilic solute are added to the solvent mixtures. Each point of the curve would move up vertically corresponding to a rapid increase of viscosity with increase of concentration. The rate of upward rise, however, is not the same at every point on the curve. As will be apparent from any series of experimental viscosity curves already given, the two extremes rise more rapidly than the central portions. As a result, as the concentration increases, there comes a point where a minimum is observed.

The whole thing is made more clear graphically by some imaginary curves as shown in Fig. 1. Between the dotted lines and the two vertical axes is the insoluble region, the slight slant of the dotted lines implying the experimentally observed fact that, the higher the concentration of the lyophilic solute, the broader is the available solvent composition range. Two types of minima are observable. In Fig. 1 (a) is shown the minimum first making its appearance at one extreme of the available composition and gradually moving towards the central sector with increase of concentration, in Fig. 1 (b), the minimum is first noticeable somewhere in the central

portion of the solvent compositions. This happens when due to the slow upward motion of the left hand compositions, the flattening of the curve first takes place right in the workable region.

FIG. 1.

Viscosity curves of a solvent mixture with increasing conc. of the lyophilic solute.

The above qualitative description leads to a very important deduction. We have proved conclusively both theoretically and experimentally that increase of concentration always shifts the minimum viscosity towards the optimum solvent composition. This qualitative picture shows that there is more chance for the minimum to make its appearance near the less viscous component; or more precisely stated, the minimum has to move from the less viscous to the more viscous component. Hence, we come to the very important conclusion that *the minimum viscosity should usually lie between the pure less viscous component and the optimum solvent composition, and should tend to move towards the latter composition with increasing solute concentration.*

This conclusion will be referred to later as *the rule of minimum viscosity*, applicable to lyophilic solutes in mixtures of two latent solvents, or of one solvent and another latent solvent. Presumably we shall look for a perfect validity of the rule in solvent mixtures whose viscosity-com-

position curve shows only a sag but no maximum or minimum. It is also assumed that no chemical combination of the solvents in the accepted sense takes place, for example, aniline-acetic acid type mixtures do not come under this rule.

That the viscosity of the individual solvents is an important factor was, perhaps, realised by McBain (*loc.cit.*). It was not realised, however, that whatever disparity in viscosity lies between the two individual latent solvents, the viscosity minimum is bound to appear with high concentration of nitrocellulose.

The rule of minimum viscosity may be more concretely put as follows. We have already shown (*vide* Part IV) that the ratio of the solvent powers gives the optimum solvent composition. Hence, if there are two non-solvents, A and B, showing mixed solvent effect, and if the viscosity of A is less than that of B, then two cases may arise depending on the relative solvent powers of A and B.

Corollary A. (1)—If the solvent power of A is greater than that of B, then the viscosity minimum lies close to the pure solvent, A, and never beyond 50% of A. The more powerful is A in comparison with B, the more will be the closeness of the minimum towards the pure A side.

A. (2)—If the solvent power of A is less than that of B, the viscosity minimum may be anywhere between pure A and somewhere containing more than 50% of A, depending on the relative solvent power of the two.

A special case arises when A is a true solvent and B is a coupler (latent solvent), the expected results being given as follows:—

Corollary B. (1)—If $\eta_A < \eta_B$, the viscosity minimum will be in the first half very close to A, and with increasing concentration of the solute, will move towards a higher percentage of the coupler.

B. (2)—If $\eta_A > \eta_B$, the viscosity minimum may remain anywhere from the lowest possible to a very high percentage of the coupler (*i.e.*, up to the optimum solvent composition), and will travel towards a lower percentage of the latent solvent with increase in concentration of the solute.

Experimental Test of the Rule of Minimum Viscosity.

It is interesting to test how far these generalisations are borne out by available experimental data. Previous data on resins in mixed solvents are absent. So far the author's data on resins and cellulose derivatives are concerned, there is no single exception to this rule, the viscosity minimum being always found to lie between the pure low viscous components and the optimum solvent composition (*vide* Table I).

TABLE I.

Solute conc.	Less viscous solvent (A).	More viscous solvent (B).	* Relative solvent power. A : B.	Observed position of minimum (% B).
Shellac.				
25 to 35%	Acetone	Water	86 : 14	7-12
35 to 45%	Acetone	Glycol	36 : 64	14-25
45 to 50%	Methyl acetate	Glycol	30 : 70	42-46
25 to 35%	Acetone	Alcohol	20 : 80	15-30
Ester Gum.				
30 to 50%	Xylene	Alcohol	68 : 32	2-20
Glyptal.				
25%	Butyl acetate	Alcohol	> 50%	About 35
Ethylcellulose.				
3 to 5%	<i>cyclo</i> Hexane	<i>cyclo</i> Hexanol.	> 50% B.	15-18
5%	Toluene	Alcohol	„	About 30
Nitrocellulose.				
10 to 15%	Alcohol	Dioxane	> 50% B.	About 65

* *i.e.*, optimum solvent composition A : B.

Viscosity studies of cellulose nitrate and acetate are available to some extent though such studies, as pointed out by Sproxtton (*Third Report on Colloid Chemistry*, 1920, p. 84), are scanty before 1920. A good amount of data accumulated in the next few years, but they are of questionable reliability, particularly after the demonstration by McBain (*loc. cit.*) of the various sources of error. We choose from among the data of this period to discuss those of Mardles (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 207T; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1951; 1924, 125, 2244 on cellulose acetate and those of McBain and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) on cellulose nitrate in the light of our theory. Since viscosity data in two non-solvents are scarce, we shall make a test of corollary B of the minimum viscosity rule for solvent-coupler mixture. We shall first make clear our reasoning by illustration with a typical case. Suppose, we take the case of ethyl acetate-alcohol solutions of nitrocellulose. Viscosity of the ester is 0.441 (25°) and that of alcohol is 1.05 (at 25°). Now, ethyl acetate, a true solvent, is by far more powerful than the latent solvent, alcohol and hence, the optimum solvent composition would contain far in excess of 50% of the ester, say, 70 : 30 proportion of ester : alcohol. Hence, according to our view, the

viscosity minimum will always lie between the pure low viscosity solvent and the optimum solvent composition, *i.e.*, it must be between 0 to 30% alcohol depending on the concentration of the solute. Of course, the value 30 has here been a reasonable estimate only, but if the relative solvent power is determined by the method proposed by us, or by any other suitable method, it is possible to fix it definitely. At all events, it can never exceed 50% alcohol. From Mardles data very few cases of solvent-active solvent mixtures are available for testing our theory (particularly, corollary B). Our main contention that the viscosity minimum lies between the pure less viscous solvent and the optimum solvent composition is, however, borne out by his data and curves (ether-alcohol, cyclohexanone-benzyl alcohol, acetone-alcohol, etc.) where it is observed to lie between the pure less viscous solvent and the composition having maximum solvent power. The data of McBain and co-workers, though involving a variety of solvents, are hardly utilisable for such test, since it is impossible to find out the position of the minimum for their data on viscosity and Arrhenius constant at only two or three solvent compositions. But, in the main, no palpable exception to our rule could be found.

Some recent precise data on nitrocellulose ($\frac{1}{2}$ R.S.) (*cf.* Doolittle, *loc. cit.*) may be used for testing the rule of minimum viscosity. Doolittle has studied 8% nitrocellulose in 29 solvent combinations of which 13 are ester-alcohol mixtures. Since methanol itself is a solvent for this type of nitrocellulose (for actual value *cf.* McBain, Grant and Smith, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 38, 1217) and so cannot be regarded as a latent solvent, this rule cannot be tested in its combination with ester. Leaving out the 3 cases using methanol, all the other combinations have the ester as the less viscous component, and alcohol as the higher viscous component. Hence, according to our theory, the viscosity should either continually rise with increase of alcohol, or should show a minimum nearer the pure ester end. All the experimental curves without exception conform to this expected behavior. The viscosity data for methanol with methyl, ethyl or isopropyl acetate do not show a minimum up to 50% methanol. Perhaps, it is above 50% methanol, which may show that methanol is a more powerful solvent for $\frac{1}{2}$ R.S. cellulose nitrate than the esters. This is confirmed by independent measurement of solvent power by dilution ratio method of the same system when it is found that the addition of methanol up to 50% (data above 50% not available) continually increases the solvent power of the ester.

In the same paper, 11 cases of ketone (solvent)-alcohol (coupler) mixture are studied, all of which, in agreement with our theory, either show a

continuous rise of viscosity with increase in alcohol, or show a minimum at small proportion (5-30%) of alcohol. Doolittle could not explain why acetone fails to show a minimum viscosity, whereas our views completely explain this supposed anomaly. If Doolittle would have increased the concentration of nitrocellulose, minimum would have been observed slowly approaching towards the optimum solvent composition. The extremely low viscosity of acetone (0.32 c.p.) is admittedly responsible for such late appearance of the minimum viscosity.

Of the remaining two cases with butanol and cellosolve or methyl cellosolve, the latter system behaves in perfect agreement with our theory. There is, however, one real exception, *i.e.*, the case of cellosolve-butyl alcohol. Cellosolve is less viscous than butyl alcohol and certainly has stronger solvent power than butyl alcohol. Hence, according to our theory either the viscosity would rise with butyl alcohol, or it should show a minimum at somewhere less than 50% butyl alcohol. The given data show that up to 60% butyl alcohol the viscosity continually decreases. We are now forced to admit it as a real departure from our rule, unless by actual experiment we are able to demonstrate a non-validity of our fundamental condition—the absence of maximum or minimum in the pure solvent mixture. From general considerations it will easily appear that only a pronounced minimum towards the alcohol side, or maximum towards the cellosolve side in the viscosity curve of the pure solvent mixture can bring forth such departure from the rule of minimum viscosity. It may be pointed out that such singular point in viscosity curves is very common in such mixture of two hydroxylic solvents (Jaegar, "Second Report of Viscosity and Plasticity", 1938, p. 80; Spills, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 530; Hatschek, "Viscosity of Liquids", 1928, p. 136). Any way, it is of real significance that the rule can pass a test of 27 cases with only one doubtful failure. Some very recent data by Ware and Teeters (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1939, 31, 738, 1116) on viscosity of different concentrations of nitrocellulose in ester-alcohol allow a further test of our rule of minimum viscosity. Seven pure esters and seven pure alcohols have been studied in 36 combinations, each combination being provided with data for more than two concentrations of nitrocellulose, and in all these cases not a single instance is observable where the minimum or the viscosity variation is in the opposite sense to that demanded by our theory. (The value 73.2 in pure *n*-propyl acetate with 11% nitrocellulose is perhaps a misprint, as appears from the general trend of its adjoining figure; otherwise this constitutes a serious discrepancy to our theory).

Effect of Concentration and Temperature on the Position of Minimum Viscosity.

It has already been demonstrated that the effect of increasing concentration is to shift the minimum viscosity towards the optimum solvent composition. But according to the rule of minimum viscosity, the viscosity minimum is always towards the low viscosity side of the optimum solvent composition. Hence, we may state that the effect of increasing concentration is to displace the minimum towards a higher proportion of the more viscous solvent.

A lowering of temperature, so far its effect on viscosity is concerned, is normally equivalent to an increase of solute concentration. Hence, on similar grounds we may state that with decrease of temperature the viscosity minimum shifts towards a higher proportion of the more viscous component. The nearer are the systems to the gelation region, the more pronounced will be the effect. These deductions from theory are in good agreement with our observations.

It would have been interesting to study rubber, which also shows pronounced augmentation of solvent power by addition of hydroxylic non-solvents (*cf. Gee, Trans. Faraday Soc., 1940, 36, 1162, 1171; Kemp and Peters, Ind. Eng. Chem., 1941, 33, 1264*) to test our view point, but unfortunately no viscosity data in mixed solvents are available.

Critical Examination of the Theory.

There are two fundamental and crucial points in our arguments. Firstly we have defined the optimum solvent composition as that composition of the solvent mixture which requires the highest concentration of the lyophilic solute to just produce gel at any given temperature. Since the composition, as defined above, is difficult of experimental determination, we have chosen to call that composition as the optimum one, which has the least tendency to gel-formation on cooling. Such an assumption has been found to be approximately justified on experimental grounds. It then follows from definition that since this composition can stand highest concentration of solute without gelling, the viscosity minimum will always tend to approach this composition with increase of solute concentration and should ultimately coincide with it in the limiting case of using of the highest workable concentration of the solute which just gives gel. Hence, it is clear that the assumption that the viscosity minimum will drift towards and finally coincide with the optimum solvent composition, is a sound one based on perfectly

logical theoretical considerations and is amply supported by experimental data. Secondly, it will be evident by following the arguments that we advanced when deducing the minimum viscosity rule in conjunction with its accompanying series of curves (Fig. 1) that, if the viscosity minimum has to occur and to drift towards the optimum composition, the simplest geometrical possibility is that the minimum should first make its appearance by the low viscosity side of the optimum solvent composition. Hence, it is established that if the basic conditions (*i.e.* no maxima or minima in the viscosity of the pure solvent mixture, no chemical combination, etc.) are satisfied, the rule of viscosity minimum follows as a logical deduction.

In attempting to apply it to actual cases we have made the assumption that the proportions of the individual solvents at the optimum composition respectively represent their solvent power. We have already discussed in a previous paper (Part IV) the validity of such an assumption and may only state that so far, we have not met with any case in conflict with this. Experiments are, however, in progress to make a crucial unambiguous test of such an hypothesis on the lines pointed out earlier, results of which only can pronounce the final verdict. But it must be pointed out that the admissibility or otherwise of such an assumption in no way affects the validity of our rule. Only it will not remain as easy as now to foretell from solvent power data (preferably, by gelation or precipitation method) the expected range in which to expect the viscosity minimum, and its direction of drift with concentration of the lyophilic solute.

It should be recognised that our theory is only applicable to cases of mixtures of two complimentary latent solvents or of a solvent and a coupler, but does not extend to mixtures of pure solvents. This limitation is due to the fact that our assumption that an optimum solvent composition exists, may not always be true in these latter cases. It may quite happen that two good solvents on mixing may antagonise each other's solvency in such a way that a mixture may gel at a lesser concentration of the solute than the individual pure solvents. Under such circumstances, viscosity maximum may be observable and this may perhaps be the cause of the viscosity maximum of shellac dissolved in a mixture of two good solvents,* alcohol and acetic acid (*cf.* Mardles, *loc. cit.*¹).

Irregular Solvents and the Rule of Minimum Viscosity.

Two sharply differentiated types of cases may be recognised from geometrical consideration. Firstly, if the minimum is between the optimum solvent composition and the low viscosity component, geometrical considerations show that the rule will be obeyed throughout; if the minimum of the pure

mixture is on the other side of the optimum composition, there is hardly any chance of the rule being valid. For the case of maximum, just the reverse holds with somewhat lesser degree of certainty. These deductions are so easily made from a consideration of the geometrical possibilities of the curves similar to those in Fig. 1 that detailed discussions are omitted.

According to Mardles (*loc. cit.*) the colloid only makes prominent any peculiarity in the viscosity curve of the pure solvent mixture. In other words if two solvents show viscosity maximum in mixture, on adding a lyophilic colloid the maximum will be more prominent.

This rule evidently cannot hold good in mixtures of two complimentary latent solvents or of a solvent and a coupler as we have established, both theoretically and experimentally, that at sufficient concentration of the lyophilic solute a minimum in viscosity curve is bound to appear independent of the nature of the viscosity curve of the pure solvent mixture. The example of acetone-water mixture is a very apt one to illustrate the inadequacy of Mardles' view. This mixture is well-known (*Int. Critical Tabl. Vol. V. p. 22*) to show viscosity minimum when cellulose acetate, cellulose nitrate or shellac is dissolved in it.

Latent Solvent and Diluent.

A diluent is a substance whose solvent power is practically nil in comparison with a true solvent. Hence, there is no optimum solvent composition except practically on the pure solvent itself. It therefore, follows from what we have said above, that the minimum, if any, should tend to

FIG. 2.

Viscosity change of a solvent-diluent mixture with increasing concentration of nitrocellulose.

approach the pure solvent with increasing concentration. It is not true that on replacing a part of the solvent by a diluent, the viscosity of the nitrocellulose solution always increases as proved from the following simple consideration. If the solvent-diluent viscosity curve is of the simple type showing no maximum or minimum, two possibilities (Fig. 2) may occur depending on whether the diluent has higher or lower viscosity. As more and more solute is added, the two curves slowly go up and assume the successive forms as shown. Evidently, in type 1, diluent will always be found to increase the viscosity, whereas in type 2, the diluent with increasing concentration of nitrocellulose first decreases the viscosity then may show minimum viscosity and finally at high concentrations of nitrocellulose shows the usual behaviour. Since most investigations on nitrocellulose, have so far been carried out at high viscosity, these points have been missed. That actually at a lower concentration of nitrocellulose, the curve for a low viscosity diluent tends to show minimum, is clearly brought out by the quite recent data of Ware and Bruner (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1940, 32, 78) for nitrocellulose in isobutyl acetate-toluene mixture as shown in the table below (see particularly data for 8% nitrocellulose).

TABLE II.

<i>iso</i> Butyl acetate : toluene.	Viscosity (sec.) at 25° for nitrocellulose conc. (g./100 cc.)			
	7 g.	8 g.	9 g.	10 g.
100 : 0	—	42.0	54.0	71.0
80 : 20	—	41.5	55.6	78.5
90 : 40	38.8	48.4	62.7	89.7
50 : 50	39.0	52.3	71.9	—
40 : 60	46.3	67.3	101.0	—

Further, it is interesting to observe from a table compiled by McBain (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 58, 1217) that in perfect agreement with our views, toluene (non-solvent) shows improved solvency (presumably viscosity lowering) with alcohol for an alcohol-soluble nitrocellulose, whereas with acetone, it does not give any optimum composition. It may be noted that the viscosity of the diluent (toluene) is lower than that of alcohol but much higher than that of acetone. So, the distinction between an active solvent and a diluent is, that for the latter in combination with a pure solvent the optimum solvent composition is practically the pure solvent itself, while for the former it contains some proportion of the active solvent. Hence, the current idea that a diluent always increases the viscosity is found to be misleading at times.

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